

Gravimetric Estimation of Potassium, Rubidium and Caesium by Zirconium Sulphate Method.

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A number of more or less satisfactory methods are available for the gravimetric estimation of potassium, the more important of which are platinum chloride (Clowes and Coleman, "Analytical Chemistry," 9th ed., p. 250), sodium hydrogen tartrate (*Ajon. Giorn. Chim. Ind. Appl.*, 1920, 2, 422), perchloric acid (Hager and Kern, *Landw. Ver. Stat.*, 1915, 87, 365), and sodium cobaltinitrite (Hamid, *Analyst*, 1926, 51, 450) methods. In spite of a large number of attempts made to improve these methods, a perusal of the literature shows that all these methods have their limitations in one respect or the other and none of these serve as a universal method.

Reed and Withrow (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1515), as the result of a large number of qualitative experiments carried on by them, have shown that it is possible to detect, by the help of zirconium sulphate solution, even very low concentrations of potassium (0.5 mg.) from potassium sulphate solutions if no interfering ions are present. They have further shown that the sensitiveness of the zirconium sulphate test is as great as that of the sodium cobaltinitrite test provided that the solutions are allowed to stand for a longer time, in cold, after mixing. It has further been pointed out by the same workers that this test can also be used for the detection of potassium even in the presence of lithium, rubidium, caesium or magnesium (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1062). This last observation appears rather an unusual one on the face of the observed and accepted similarity between the other properties of potassium, rubidium, and caesium. It is also contradictory to the previous work of Rosenheim and Frank (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 812) who showed that rubidium and caesium zirconyl sulphates could be prepared in exactly similar ways as the corresponding potassium salt. The reason why Reed and Withrow could not detect

the formation of these salts of rubidium and caesium was probably due to the fact that in their experiments, as compared to the amount of potassium salt taken, they had been using such small quantities of rubidium and caesium as would not have given any formation of the precipitate at the ordinary temperatures. Also, they had been using acidic solutions of the zirconium salt for their experiments, the use of which the authors have found to be detrimental to the precipitation of these double salts.

Taking into consideration the observations of Rosenheim and Frank, and Reed and Withrow, it appeared quite interesting to the authors to examine if it could be possible to utilise this method as one of the alternative methods for the gravimetric estimation of potassium, rubidium and caesium.

Moreover as Reed and Withrow were concerned with the qualitative side of the problem only, they never tried to ascertain the composition of the double compounds formed as the result of the reaction between potassium sulphate and zirconium sulphate. It appeared, therefore, also necessary to determine the exact condition under which complete reactions between the two solutions take place and the composition of the compound so formed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(a) *The Preparation of Solutions.*

Zirconium sulphate solution.—22 G. of Merck's "extra pure" zirconium sulphate were heated in a porcelain crucible for 15 minutes on a blow-pipe flame. The heated substance was put in 100 c. c. of cold distilled water, stirred continuously for half an hour and finally filtered. This gave a saturated solution of the salt which was preserved in a clean glass-stoppered bottle. A fresh sample of the zirconium sulphate solution was prepared in a similar manner every day, since the solution undergoes hydrolysis on keeping for more than 48 hours.

Potassium, rubidium and caesium sulphate solutions were prepared in the usual way using Merck's "extra pure" substances.

Sodium cobaltinitrite solution was prepared by Hamid's method. (*loc. cit.*).

Potassium chloride and the perchloric acid solutions were prepared in the usual manner.

(b) *Determination of the Composition of the Double Salts formed and the Study of the Conditions under which they are obtained.*

A very large variety of the double salts of potassium with zirconium sulphate have been reported by various workers (Berzelius, Franz, Warren, Rosenheim and Frank, J. W. Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic Theoretical Chemistry, 1927, pp. 157-159; *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 812) to have been obtained under varying conditions. Of all these reported compounds, the following three have the greatest stability and are easily prepared by the direct action of potassium sulphate (acid or normal) on the zirconium sulphate solution:—

while the rest of them are comparatively less stable and more difficult to prepare. Hence on account of these advantages only these compounds were studied.

As a result of a large number of preliminary experiments it was noticed that the compound $3K_2O, 3ZrO_2, 7SO_3, 9H_2O$, was obtained by the action of an acidified solution of zirconium sulphate on acid potassium sulphate, while the compound $2K_2O, 6ZrO_2, 7SO_3, 9H_2O$ was obtained when normal potassium sulphate was used. However, these compounds are not suitable for the gravimetric estimation of potassium, since they are fairly soluble and difficult to precipitate completely.

The compound having the composition $Zr_2O_3(KSO_4)_2, 8H_2O$ was obtained by the action of a neutral solution of zirconium sulphate on normal potassium sulphate. This compound has an advantage over the other two compounds in being comparatively easily and completely precipitated. It may be mentioned that the difficulty in completely precipitating the other two compounds is to a large extent due to the presence of free acid in the solutions.

For these reasons our choice was naturally in favour of this last compound for the gravimetric estimation of potassium.

(c) *The Gravimetric Estimation of Potassium.*

In all the experiments in which the estimations of potassium were carried out by the zirconium sulphate method, exactly 10 c. c. of the potassium sulphate solution of varying concentrations were taken

in clean dry beakers. Equal volumes of concentrated solutions of zirconium sulphate were added. The mixture after shaking was allowed to stand at 0° for two or three hours. The precipitate was transferred to a weighed Gooch crucible, washed first with a little cold water, then with a 5% solution of alcohol and finally with ether. It was then dried at 130° to a constant weight. The residue so obtained was analysed and it had the composition represented by the formula, $Zr_2O_3(K_2SO_4)_2$, from which the percentage of potassium was calculated. The results of a large number of experiments on the estimation of potassium from potassium sulphate solutions along with the results obtained on potassium estimations with the other well-known methods are given in the following table.

TABLE I.

Calc. amt. of potassium in the sample.	Amount of potassium in g. found in the sample.		
	Zirconium sulphate method.	Sodium cobalt-nitrite method.	Perchlorate method.*
0.8590 g.	0.8587 g.	0.8589 g.	0.8586 g.
0.8231	0.8228	0.8225	0.8221
0.2872	0.2868	0.2868	0.2869
0.2518	0.2509	0.2512	0.2508
0.2154	0.2145	0.2150	0.2149
0.1795	0.1788	0.1787	0.1789
0.1486	0.1484	0.1481	0.1480
0.1077	0.1072	0.1074	0.1072
0.0718	0.0715	0.0715	0.0712
0.0259	0.0256	0.0257	0.0256
0.0179	0.0178	0.0178	0.0177

(d) *Influence of the Presence of the Ammonium Ions on the Accuracy and Sensitivity of the Zirconium Sulphate Method.*

It is a well-known fact that perchloric acid, chloroplatinic acid and sodium cobaltinitrite methods fail to give satisfactory results when ammonium ions are present. Therefore, experiments were carried out to see if the present method would work in the presence of ammo-

* For the estimation of potassium by perchlorate method, solutions of potassium chloride having the same concentrations of potassium as in the corresponding potassium sulphate solutions were used.

rium ions, or not. For this purpose, 5 c. c. of a 10 per cent. solution of ammonium sulphate were added to 5 c. c. of a potassium sulphate solution and thoroughly shaken together, then 5 c. c. of a concentrated solution of the zirconium sulphate were added so as to make a total volume of 15 c. c. A number of experiments were carried out in which the concentration of the potassium sulphate solution was varied and that of the other solutions was kept constant. The results of the experiments are scheduled in the following table

TABLE II.

Zirconium sulphate solution = 5 c. c. of a 20.11 % solution.
 Potassium sulphate solution = 5 c. c. of varying strength.
 Ammonium sulphate solution = 5 c. c. of a 10 % solution.

Calculated amount of potassium in the sample	Amount of potassium found in the sample
0.1077 g.	0.1078 g
0.0718	0.0716
0.0350	0.0350
0.0170	0.0170
0.0000	0.0003

The results given in the above table quite clearly show that the presence of ammonium ions in no way interferes with the estimation of potassium by the zirconium sulphate method. This is a distinct advantage over the other methods. This conclusion is in agreement with the recent publication of the results and conclusion of Reed and Withrow (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2985).

(c) *Influence of the Presence of Sodium and Lithium Ions on the Accuracy of the Zirconium Sulphate Method.*

Reed and Withrow (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1515) have found out qualitatively that the presence of a large amount of sodium sulphate in the potassium sulphate solution retarded the detection of potassium in concentrated solutions but had very little or no effect when dilute solutions were used. As a result of a large number of preliminary experiments it was found also by us that the time required for the complete precipitation of potassium with zirconium

sulphate went on increasing with the increase in the quantity of sodium sulphate added to the potassium sulphate solution.

Experiments were therefore carried out to find out whether the presence of sodium ions and also that of lithium ions had any influence on the accuracy of the method.

The results of a series of experiments carried out with a view to study the influence of the presence of sodium and lithium ions on the method under investigation are given in the following table : —

TABLE III.

Zirconium sulphate solution = 8 c. c. of 20.11 % solution

Potassium sulphate solution = 2 c. c. of 8 % solution.

Sodium or lithium sulphate solution = 5 c. c. of varying strengths.

Total volume = 15 c. c.

Calculated amount of potassium in each sample = 0.0718 g.

<i>Effect of sodium ions.</i>		<i>Effect of lithium ions.</i>	
Amt. of sodium sulphate added.	Potassium experimentally found.	Amt. of lithium sulphate added.	Potassium experimentally found.
0.01 g.	0.0716 g.	0.0105 g.	0.0714 g.
0.02	0.0714	0.0250	0.0713
0.04	0.0718	0.1000	0.0718
0.06	0.0718	0.1000	0.0712
0.08	0.0717	0.2000	0.0716
0.10	0.0718	0.3000	0.0717
0.12	0.0709	0.0000	0.0714
0.14	0.0711	0.5000	0.0714
0.16	0.0714	0.6000	0.0712
0.18	0.0715	0.7000	0.0716
0.20	0.0717	0.8000	0.0715
		0.9000	0.0717
		1.0000	0.0716

Gravimetric Estimation of Rubidium and Caesium.

All the methods which are used for the estimation of potassium are used for the estimation of rubidium and caesium too, since there is a great similarity in the properties of these elements. This close similarity between these elements suggested the idea of the zirconium sulphate method for the estimation of the other two members, beside potassium of the family.

When a neutral solution of zirconium sulphate is added to a saturated solution of rubidium sulphate, a white crystalline precipitate gradually comes down. This precipitate was taken on a weighed filterpaper, washed first with cold water, then with alcohol and finally with ether and dried in a steam oven. The analysis of a number of samples of the compound so prepared showed the composition to correspond to the formula, $Zr_2O_3.(RbSO_4)_2.15H_2O$.

With caesium sulphate and zirconium sulphate, a compound with the composition, $Zr_2O_3.(CsSO_4)_2.11H_2O$ is obtained. Thus the double salts obtained by the action of neutral zirconium sulphate on normal rubidium and caesium sulphate are similar to the corresponding potassium salt with the only difference in the number of the molecules of water of crystallisation.

Rubidium and caesium were thus precipitated as double salts by normal zirconium sulphate solution. The method followed in their precipitations and estimations was exactly the same as described under the "Gravimetric estimation of potassium."

In the following tables, the results of the estimations of rubidium and caesium from their respective sulphate solutions by the zirconium sulphate method have been tabulated.

TABLE IV.

<i>Rubidium.</i>		<i>Caesium.</i>	
Calculated amt. of rubidium in the sample.	Amt. of rubidium experimentally found out.	Calculated amt. of caesium in the sample.	Amt. of caesium experimentally found out.
0.1033 g.	0.1080 g.	0.1249 g.	0.1245 g.
0.0990	0.0929	0.1124	0.1120
0.0827	0.0825	0.0999	0.0994
0.0723	0.0721	0.0874	0.0872
0.0620	0.0616	0.0749	0.0745
0.0517	0.0514	0.0624	0.0621
0.0413	0.0411	0.0499	0.0496
0.0310	0.0309	0.0375	0.0373
0.0207	0.0206	0.0250	0.0248
0.0104	0.0102	0.0125	0.0122

TABLE V.

Effect of Ammonium Ions.

2 C.c. of rubidium or caesium sulphate solution.

5 C.c. of 20·13% zirconium sulphate solution.

3 C.c. of ammonium sulphate solution of varying strength.

Total volume = 10 c.c.

Amount of ammonium sulphate in the sample.	<i>Rubidium sulphate.</i>		<i>Caesium sulphate.</i>	
	Calc. amount of rubidium in the sample.	Amt. of rubidium found experimentally.	Calculated amt. of caesium in the sample.	Amount of caesium found experimentally.
0·0052 g.	0·0413 g.	0·0410 g.	0·0499 g.	0·0497 g.
0·0125	0·0413	0·0411	0·0499	0·0497
0·0250	0·0413	0·0409	0·0499	0·0498
0·0500	0·0413	0·0412	0·0499	0·0498
0·1000	0·0413	0·0410	0·0499	0·0495
0·2000	0·0413	0·0409	0·0499	0·0496
0·3000	0·0413	0·0411	0·0499	0·0496
0·4000	0·0413	0·0412	0·0499	0·0497
0·5000	0·0413	0·0408	0·0499	0·0496
0·6000	0·0413	0·0409	0·0499	0·0499

TABLE VI.

Effect of Sodium Ions.

2 C.c. of rubidium or caesium sulphate solution.

5 C.c. of 20·13% zirconium sulphate solution.

3 C.c. of sodium sulphate solution of varying concentrations.

Total volume = 10 c.c.

Amt. of sodium sulphate in the sample.	<i>Rubidium sulphate.</i>		<i>Caesium sulphate.</i>	
	Calc. amt. of rubidium in the sample.	Amt. of rubidium found out experimentally.	Calc. amt. of caesium in the sample.	Amount of caesium found out experimentally
0·0025 g.	0·0413 g.	0·0411 g.	0·0499 g.	0·0496 g.
0·0050	0·0413	0·0408	0·0499	0·0497
0·0100	0·0413	0·0409	0·0499	0·0498
0·0200	0·0413	0·0410	0·0499	0·0495
0·0400	0·0413	0·0411	0·0499	0·0497
0·0600	0·0413	0·0409	0·0499	0·0496
0·0800	0·0413	0·0409	0·0499	0·0498
0·1000	0·0413	0·0410	0·0499	0·0496
0·1200	0·0413	0·0411	0·0499	0·0498

TABLE VII.

Effect of Lithium Ions.

- 2 C.c. of rubidium or caesium sulphate solution.
 5 C.c. of 20.13% zirconium sulphate solution.
 3 C.c. of lithium sulphate solution of varying concentrations.
 Total volume=10 c.c.

Amt. of lithium sulphate in the sample.	<i>Rubidium sulphate.</i>		<i>Caesium sulphate.</i>	
	Calc. amt. of rubidium in the sample.	Amt. of rubidium found out experimentally.	Calc. amt. of caesium in the sample.	Amount of caesium found out experimentally.
0.0003 g.	0.0413 g.	0.0411 g.	0.0499 g.	0.0497 g.
0.0006	0.0413	0.0410	0.0499	0.0496
0.0012	0.0413	0.0412	0.0499	0.0496
0.0025	0.0413	0.0411	0.0499	0.0497
0.0500	0.0413	0.0410	0.0499	0.0495
0.1000	0.0413	0.0412	0.0499	0.0498
0.2000	0.0413	0.0410	0.0499	0.0496
0.4000	0.0413	0.0411	0.0499	0.0497
0.6000	0.0413	0.0411	0.0499	0.0498

Summary.

1. Potassium, rubidium and caesium can be estimated accurately by precipitating them in the form of the double salts with zirconium sulphate provided that such interfering ions as would also react with either zirconium or the sulphate ions to give insoluble precipitates are previously eliminated. The results obtained by this method are as accurate as those obtained by the sodium cobaltinitrite and the perchloric acid methods (*vide* Table I).

2. In order to estimate potassium, rubidium or caesium by this method they should be present in the form of sulphates. This is, however, by no means difficult since almost all the well-known compounds of these elements are easily converted into the corresponding sulphates on treatment with sulphuric acid.

3. This method does not serve satisfactorily in acidic solutions.

4. The presence of ammonium ions in the solutions of the sulphates of either potassium, rubidium or caesium does not in any way interfere with the accuracy of this method. This is a distinct advantage over the sodium cobaltinitrite, the platinum chloride and the perchloric acid method (*vide* Tables II and V).

5. The presence of sodium ions beyond prolonging the time required for complete precipitation in no way interferes with the accurate determination of these elements (*vide* Tables III and VI).

6. The presence of lithium ions, too, has no effect on the accuracy of this method (*vide* Tables III and VII).

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